

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**ASSESSMENT OF ATTAINMENT OF CARDIOVASCULAR
TARGETS IN DIABETIC PATIENTS AND FACTORS
FORECASTING GOAL ACCOMPLISHMENT**Dr. Iqra Razzaq¹, Dr. Ayesha Hashmi², Dr. Afsah Farooq³^{1, 2, 3} Fatima Jinnah Medical University, Lahore**Article Received:** March 2020**Accepted:** April 2020**Published:** May 2020**Abstract:**

Treatment of type 2 diabetes requires control of hyperglycemia, hyperlipidemia, and close monitoring of hypertension. Measuring exposure to these factors helps assess patients' risk for primary cardiovascular prophylaxis, and achieving goals helps control the cardiovascular system.

Place and Duration: *In the Medicine Units of Jinnah Hospital Lahore for one year duration from February 2019 to February 2020.*

Patients and methods: *A cross-sectional study was performed on three hundred patients who referred to hospitals and outpatient clinics. Three basic parameters of HbA1c, systolic blood pressure and LDL-C have been registered. Patients were divided into two groups as HbA1c $\leq 7\%$, systolic blood pressure ≤ 140 mmHg and LDL-C ≤ 100 mg / dl in accordance with the above-mentioned objectives. Patients who achieved all three goals were compared with those who did not achieve diabetes, body mass index, and glucose lowering therapy, cardiovascular therapy, and micro- and macro vascular complications.*

Results: *Out of 300 patients, only 14 patients achieved all three goals and 102 patients did not achieve any of these goals ($p = 0.021$). There was no significant difference between the two groups of patients in terms of micro- and macro-vascular complications ($p = 0.48$). There was no significant difference in cardiovascular treatment between the two groups ($p = 0.52$). There was no significant difference between diabetes ($p = 0.41$), gender ($p = 0.38$), body mass index ($p = 0.64$) and duration of diabetes (diabetes ($p = 0.56$)). However, the study population has a high incidence of obesity.*

Conclusion: *A low percentage of diabetic patients meets all recommended goals. Good blood pressure, blood sugar and hyperlipidemia are recommended to prevent complications in diabetic patients.*

Corresponding author:**Dr Iqra Razzaq,**

Fatima Jinnah Medical University, Lahore

QR code

Please cite this article in press Iqra Razzaq et al, *Assessment Of Attainment Of Cardiovascular Targets In Diabetic Patients And Factors Forecasting Goal Accomplishment.*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2020; 07(05).

INTRODUCTION:

The management of type 2 diabetes requires close monitoring of hyperglycemia, hyperlipidemia and hypertension, three key quality indicators to prevent cardiovascular complications, i.e. glycosylated hemoglobin (HbA1c) (A), systolic blood pressure (B) and LDL cholesterol (C). Measuring exposure to these factors helps assess patients' risk for primary cardiovascular prophylaxis, and achieving goals helps control the cardiovascular system¹. Severe depression was significantly correlated ($p = 0.048$) with lower (25.4%) rates of achieving the ABC goal than those without depression (5.0%). A characteristic feature of diabetic dyslipidemia is high plasma triglyceride levels, low HDL levels and elevated LDL cholesterol levels. It can be complicated by diabetes, coronary artery disease, stroke, peripheral arterial disease. Patients with diabetes have an increased risk of developing heart disease, and patients with cardiovascular disease diagnosed with diabetes have a negative prognosis. Overweight and obesity have contributed to an increase in the incidence of diabetes. Patients with type 2 diabetes have been reported to have endothelial dysfunction². Gluco-metabolic and cardiovascular disorders are related. Hypoglycemia is a hallmark of diabetes. Contributes to myocardial damage after ischemic events. Both pre-diabetes and metabolic syndrome increase the risk of diabetes, even in patients with normoglycemia³. There is a strong relationship between any form of gluco-metabolic disorder and heart failure. Hyperglycemia, hyperlipidemia, hypertension and micro albuminuria are the main risk factors for a higher incidence of coronary heart disease⁴. Controlling your diabetes AUC may reduce the risk of stroke ischemic heart disease. According to the World Health Organization, 75% of patients with non-insulin-dependent diabetes die of vascular events. Metabolic syndrome is a group of risk factors responsible for the majority of cardiovascular diseases in people with type 2 diabetes⁵. Metabolic syndrome increases the risk of coronary heart disease and stroke three times. Mortality from cardiovascular causes, which is why diabetes is considered a vascular disease that has been diagnosed with high blood sugar⁶. Abnormal vascular findings associated with atherosclerosis, coronary artery calcification in patients with diabetes mellitus, medial carotid artery thickness and vascular endothelial dysfunction are specific vascular symptoms in diabetes⁷. Evidence suggests that LDL.C > 100 mg / dl is associated with an increased cardiovascular risk. Considering the above facts, we examined glycemic control by HbA1 measurement, blood pressure control by measuring systolic blood pressure (SBP) and lipid control by measuring low density lipoprotein cholesterol (LDL.C). Diabetic patients.

OBJECTIVES AND OBJECTIVES OF THE RESEARCH

1. To evaluate the patients of diabetes mellitus patients attaining, LDL.c < 100mg/dl, Systolic blood pressure < 130mmHg and HbA1c < 7%.
2. To compare the goal achievers with non-achievers for factors predicting goal achievement i: e age, sex, body mass index (BMI), glucose lowering drugs micro & macro vascular complications.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

The study included patients with diabetes who participated in the clinical and outpatient department of Jinnah Hospital Lahore for one year duration from February 2019 to February 2020.

Patients with other diseases besides diabetes were excluded: malignancies, primary kidney disease, congenital heart disease, and vasculitis. Sample Size. The sample size is calculated using the formula given

$$n = \frac{2(Z_{\alpha} + Z_{1-\beta})^2 \sigma^2}{\Delta^2}$$

$$\Delta^2$$

Z is 1.96. Z is 0.8416. The standard deviation (based on the data in the published article) will be about 0.7. The required difference (estimated effect size) as a result of the two interventions required is 15%. The approximate size of the registered sample was 300 patients. There were 300 patients who reported to the Lahore Hospital Outpatient Clinic and the Khair-un-nisa Lahore Hospital from June 1, 2014 to December 31, 2014. If fasting plasma glucose (FPG) ≥ 126 mg / dl (7, 0 mmol / l) or random plasma glucose ≥ 200 mg / dl (11.1 mmol / l) or plasma glucose ≥ 200 , the patient has been diagnosed with diabetes. mg / dl (11.1 mmol / l) 75 g or HbA1C < 6.5% confirmed twice after glucose loading. All patients had three basic HbA1c parameters, systolic blood pressure and LDL-C. Patients were divided according to the above-mentioned HbA1c values $\leq 7\%$, systolic blood pressure ≤ 140 mm Hg and target values LDL-C ≤ 100 mg / dl. Patients who achieved all three goals were included in one group, patients who did not achieve any goals or could not achieve one or two goals, were included in another group. Both groups were compared for diabetes, body mass index and glucose lowering therapy, cardiovascular therapy, and micro- and macro-vascular complications.

Registered variables were the fasting lipid profile, including age, type of diabetes, duration of diabetes, HbA1c, LDL. Drugs that lower glucose, including cholesterol (LDL.C), albuminuria, micro- and macro-vascular complications of body mass index, insulin and cardiovascular therapy. Hypertension was defined as systolic blood pressure ≥ 140 mmHg

and diastolic blood pressure ≥ 90 mmHg. Coronary artery disease has been diagnosed based on history (myocardial infarction, percutaneous coronary intervention or coronary artery bypass graft) or exercise tolerance test or echocardiography. Peripheral arterial disease was defined on the basis of claudication / traces of diabetic foot. Peripheral neuropathy was diagnosed based on signs of numbness and clinical sensory examination. Diabetic retinopathy was diagnosed by patient fundoscopy.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

Frequencies are defined as mean and standard deviation. The significance of the difference between means was analyzed using the chi-square test. The difference between the results was considered significant or not significant for $p < 0.05$ respectively. Data were analyzed using SPSS version 20.

RESULTS:

The average age of 300 patients was 51. (Figure 1) Average fasting glucose 173 mg / dl, 10% of patients

with type 1 diabetes, 90% of patients with type 2 diabetes 2.50.7% (152), while 49, 3% of patients (148) women. 70% of patients have HbA1c above 7%. 75% have LDL. C > 100 mg / dl. In 72% of patients, systolic blood pressure is over 140 mmHg (Table 1). In 78% of patients, BMI is > 30% (Table 2). 26% of patients have diabetes above 10 years. (Figure 2). Of the 300 patients, only 14 patients achieved all three goals and 102 patients did not achieve any of these goals ($p = 0.021$), the remaining patients (184) only achieved one or two goals. 95.34% of patients were not met, and only 4.66% of them achieved three goals. In 18 patients, systolic blood pressure was less than 140 mmHg ($p = 0.084$) and HbA1c < 7%. ($P = 0.005$). 36% of the study population used metformin, 26% of the study population used a combination of insulin, and 19% of the study population used a combination of oral hypoglycemic agents. (Fig. 3). 81 % of patients had micro- and macrovascular complications (Fig. 4), and only 40% of patients received cardiovascular treatment. (Fig. 5) 8.17% (23) of patients suffered from coronary heart disease, 12.66% (38) of patients suffered from kidney disease.

Figure 1: Age of Patients

Figure 2 : Duration of diabetes mellitus in patients**Table 1: Correlation of HB A1c (%) * LDL-c * systolic blood pressure**

Systolic Blood Pressure			LDL-c		Total	Significance
			<100mg/dl	>100mg/dl		
<140mmHg	HB A1c (%)	Less or equal 7	14	18	32	0.116
		More than 7	16	36	52	
	Total		30	54	84	
>140mmHg	HB A1c (%)	Less or equal 7	18	41	59	0.021
		More than 7	26	131	157	
	Total		44	172	216	

Table 2: Body Mass Index

Study population	body mass index		Total
	<30	>30	
Selected (three target achievers)	3	11	14
Not Selected (three target non-achievers)	62	224	286
Total	65	235	300

DISCUSSION:

The aim of the study is to determine the effectiveness of glycemic control, hypertension and hyperlipidemia, which are major cardiovascular risk factors in patients with diabetes. A significant number of patients could not achieve their goal. Systolic blood pressure was relatively controlled compared to LDL. A. The main metabolic factor common in the study population was the increase in body mass index (BMI), but there was no significant difference between those who achieved the goal and those who could not⁸. Using similar cut-off points to

document optimal control of the diabetes risk ratio based on the national health and nutrition study and behavioral risk factor surveillance, the achievement of the three-target smoking ban increased from 4.6% to 14.3% between 1999 and 2010.

There was no significant difference between the micro- and macro-vascular complications between the two treatment groups. 95.34% of patients were not achieved and only 4.66% of patients achieved all three goals. Over half of the patients experienced micro- and macro-vascular complications. In our study, almost half of the patients have over five

years of diabetes, although this is not statistically significant⁹. As for cardiovascular drugs, there was no significant difference between those who achieved the goal and none. Chronic hyperglycemia and hypertension synergistically increase microvascular damage. Increased serum cholesterol works synergistically. Normoglycemia, poor blood pressure control, and the most important reason for failure to achieve LDL.C is drug abuse. Reducing the burden of cardiovascular disease in diabetes should begin with the assessment and treatment of LDL with statins are preferred. LDL.C is the main goal of lipid lowering therapy in the ADA and NCEP ATP III guidelines¹⁰. A typical lipid disorder in diabetic patients is characterized by diabetic dyslipidemia, high triglycerides, low HDL cholesterol and the increasing number of small dense LDL particles. Achieving diabetes goals is difficult and inappropriate in most clinical cases. Lowering LDL cholesterol to <70 mg / dl may provide higher cardiovascular goals, and recent guidelines recommend <70 mg / dl as the optimal LDL target for very high-risk patients, especially patients with coronary artery disease¹¹.

Sugar-vascular complications begin before diabetes occurs¹⁹. This phenomenon is explained by the increase in insulin resistance. Patients with type 2 diabetes with low HbA1c levels have a significant increase in risk of cardiovascular death and all cardiovascular events by more than 7% compared to patients with diabetes with low HbA1c¹². Many potential factors associated with failure to achieve critical goals in DM2 are barriers or restrictions in the treatment of the disease, such as statin intolerance. Another responsible factor seems to be the natural trend of variables that increase over time, which is responsible for disappointing success rates. HbA1c (28%) and SBP (30%).

The variables described demonstrate better objective intervention to improve the overall management of the main interchangeable vascular risk components¹³. Appropriate medications should be prescribed to control blood pressure, blood sugar and lipids, including combining treatment and improving lifestyle. Due to the increased risk of cardiovascular diseases, along with metabolic risk factors and hyperglycemic effects on the vascular system, the acceptance of diabetes into a particular category of risk factors increases¹⁴. The absolute risk of a serious coronary event is the same as in non-diabetic patients with established coronary artery disease. The ultimate goal of public health and clinical intervention is to prevent diabetes by reducing obesity and promoting physical activity in the general population. Women with diabetes seem to lose their natural protection against the development of cardiovascular diseases¹⁵. The prognosis for patients with diabetes is worse than for

coronary heart disease without diabetes. Most patients with microalbuminuria also have hypertension. In these patients, hypertension control reduces the reduction in glomerular filtration rate. Hypertension is a determined risk factor for cardiovascular disease. When hypertension is accompanied by open diabetes, the risk of cardiovascular disease, including kidney disease, doubles. There is a positive relationship between hypertension and insulin resistance.

CONCLUSION:

A low percentage of diabetic patients meets all recommended main goals. Good blood pressure, blood sugar and hyperlipidemia are recommended to prevent complications in diabetic patients. The study population was characterized by a high incidence of obesity, micro- and macro-vascular complications, and most patients had diabetes for over five years.

REFERENCES:

1. Breuker, Cyril, Florian Clement, Thibault Mura, Valérie Macioce, Audrey Castet-Nicolas, Yohan Audurier, Catherine Boegner et al. "Non-achievement of LDL-cholesterol targets in patients with diabetes at very-high cardiovascular risk receiving statin treatment: incidence and risk factors." *International journal of cardiology* 268 (2018): 195-199.
2. Khunti, Kamlesh, Antonio Ceriello, Xavier Cos, and Christophe De Block. "Achievement of guideline targets for blood pressure, lipid, and glycaemic control in type 2 diabetes: a meta-analysis." *Diabetes research and clinical practice* 137 (2018): 137-148.
3. Presta, Vivianne, Ilaria Figliuzzi, Francesca Miceli, Roberta Coluccia, Federica Fogacci, Arrigo Francesco Giuseppe Cicero, Andrea Ferrucci et al. "Achievement of low density lipoprotein (LDL) cholesterol targets in primary and secondary prevention: Analysis of a large real practice database in Italy." *Atherosclerosis* 285 (2019): 40-48.
4. Schmieder, Roland E., Diethelm Tschöpe, Cornelia Koch, Taoufik Ouarrak, Anselm K. Gitt, and DIALOGUE study group. "Individualised treatment targets in patients with type-2 diabetes and hypertension." *Cardiovascular diabetology* 17, no. 1 (2018): 18.
5. Meneghini, Luigi F., Didac Mauricio, Emanuela Orsi, Nebojsa M. Lalic, Anna MG Cali, Jukka Westerbacka, Peter Stella et al. "The Diabetes Unmet Need with Basal Insulin Evaluation (DUNE) study in type 2 diabetes: Achieving HbA1c targets with basal insulin in a real-world setting." *Diabetes, Obesity and Metabolism* 21, no. 6 (2019): 1429-1436.
6. Danchin, Nicolas, Wael Almahmeed, Khalid Al-Rasadi, Joseph Azuri, Abdelkrim Berrah,

- Carlos Alberto Cuneo, Yuri Karpov et al. "Achievement of low-density lipoprotein cholesterol goals in 18 countries outside Western Europe: The International Cholesterol management Practice Study (ICLPS)." *European journal of preventive cardiology* 25, no. 10 (2018): 1087-1094.
7. Sakamoto, Masaya, Daisuke Matsutani, Soichiro Minato, Yuki Tsujimoto, Yosuke Kayama, Norihiko Takeda, Seiichi Ichikawa, Ryuzo Horiuchi, Kazunori Utsunomiya, and Masako Nishikawa. "Seasonal Variations in the Achievement of Guideline Targets for HbA1c, Blood Pressure, and Cholesterol Among Patients With Type 2 Diabetes: A Nationwide Population-Based Study (ABC Study: JDDM49)." *Diabetes care* 42, no. 5 (2019): 816-823.
 8. Yan, Bryan P., Fu-Tien Chiang, Baishali Ambegaonkar, Philippe Brudi, Martin Horack, Dominik Lautsch, Ami Vyas, and Anselm K. Gitt. "Low-density lipoprotein cholesterol target achievement in patients surviving an acute coronary syndrome in Hong Kong and Taiwan-findings from the Dyslipidemia International Study II." *International journal of cardiology* 265 (2018): 1-5.
 9. Barzkar, Hamid, Hossein-Ali Nikbakht, Maryam Zeinolabedini, Towhid Babazadeh, Soheil Hassanipour, and Saber Ghaffari-fam. "Factors associated with therapeutic target achievement in the control of complications in consequence of diabetes: A hospital-based study in west of Iran." *Diabetes & Metabolic Syndrome: Clinical Research & Reviews* 13, no. 3 (2019): 2009-2013.
 10. Sonmez, Alper, Cem Haymana, Fahri Bayram, Serpil Salman, Oguzhan Sitki Dizdar, Eren Gurkan, Ayse Kargili Carlıoglu et al. "Turkish nationwide survey of glycemic and other Metabolic parameters of patients with Diabetes mellitus (TEMD study)." *diabetes research and clinical practice* 146 (2018): 138-147.
 11. Leiter, Lawrence A., Alice YY Cheng, Jean-Marie Ekoé, Ronald M. Goldenberg, Stewart B. Harris, Irene M. Hramiak, Kamlesh Khunti et al. "Glycated hemoglobin level goal achievement in adults with type 2 diabetes in Canada: still room for improvement." *Canadian journal of diabetes* 43, no. 6 (2019): 384-391.
 12. Zhang, Yu-Qing, Yong Li, Yu-Gang Dong, Yan-Hua Wu, Rui Bian, Ji-Hu Li, and Li-Nong Ji. "A nationwide assessment of blood pressure control and the associated factors in Chinese type 2 diabetes mellitus patients." *The Journal of Clinical Hypertension* 21, no. 11 (2019): 1654-1663.
 13. Duff, Christopher J., Ivonne Solis-Trapala, Owen J. Driskell, David Holland, Helen Wright, Jenna L. Waldron, Clare Ford et al. "The frequency of testing for glycated haemoglobin, HbA1c, is linked to the probability of achieving target levels in patients with suboptimally controlled diabetes mellitus." *Clinical Chemistry and Laboratory Medicine (CCLM)* 57, no. 2 (2018): 296-304.
 14. März, Winfried, Franz-Werner Dippel, Karlheinz Theobald, Katherine Gorcyca, Șerban R. Iorga, and David Ansell. "Utilization of lipid-modifying therapy and low-density lipoprotein cholesterol goal attainment in patients at high and very-high cardiovascular risk: Real-world evidence from Germany." *Atherosclerosis* 268 (2018): 99-107.
 15. American Diabetes Association. "9. Cardiovascular disease and risk management: standards of medical care in diabetes—2018." *Diabetes care* 41, no. Supplement 1 (2018): S86-S104.